

On-Sky Results of a Real-Time Adaptive Optics Controller Using Deep Learning Wavefront Sensors

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ABSTRACT

Real-time control (RTC) for Adaptive Optics (AO) in modern astronomical instruments requires both ultralow latency and high reconstruction accuracy to compensate for rapidly varying atmospheric turbulence. Recent advances in Deep Learning (DL), particularly Transformer Neural Networks (TNNs), have shown strong potential for improving wavefront estimation and control. However, deploying these models in operational AO systems remains challenging due to the strict timing constraints and hardware requirements of real-time correction. In this work, we present the optimization and on-sky deployment of a Transformer-based RTC for AO using NVIDIA TensorRT and the Durham Adaptive Optics Real-Time Controller (DAO RTC) framework. We evaluate mixed-precision inference strategies to improve computational efficiency on modern GPU architectures while preserving reconstruction performance. To reduce end-to-end latency, the system uses DAO shared memory to exchange loop variables, camera frames, and deformable mirror commands with minimal overhead, while GPU-based preprocessing handles normalization, noise filtering, and spatial transformations in real time. The proposed controller was validated in closed-loop operation on the PAPYRUS bench at the Observatoire de Haute-Provence, using a non-modulated pyramid wavefront sensor to estimate more than 200 Zernike modes. The system sustained a 700 Hz correction rate with millisecond inference latency. On-sky results show that the deep learning controller improves residual wavefront correction and Strehl ratio compared with classical reconstruction approaches. These results demonstrate the feasibility of integrating Transformer-based models into real-time AO systems and highlight their potential for next-generation astronomical instrumentation.

Keywords: Adaptive Optics, Real-Time Control, Deep Learning, Wavefront Reconstruction, Pyramid Wavefront Sensor, TensorRT, On-Sky Demonstration

1. INTRODUCTION

Adaptive Optics (AO) systems are essential for compensating atmospheric turbulence in ground-based astronomical observations[6]. Their performance strongly depends on the real-time controller (RTC), which must estimate the aberrated wavefront and apply a correction with very low latency and limited jitter[10]. These requirements become even more critical for next-generation astronomical instruments, where higher correction orders and faster control frequencies impose increasing computational demands.

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In this context, deep learning has emerged as a promising alternative to classical wavefront reconstruction techniques[1, 8]. In particular, Transformer Neural Networks (TNNs) have shown strong potential for estimating wavefront aberrations from pyramid wavefront sensor measurements, especially in regimes where nonlinearities limit the performance of conventional reconstructors[9]. However, despite their reconstruction capability, deploying such models in closed-loop AO remains challenging because inference, preprocessing, and data transfer must all satisfy strict real-time constraints.

To address these limitations, we implemented a Transformer-based RTC accelerated with NVIDIA TensorRT[5, 11] and integrated within the Durham Adaptive Optics (DAO) framework[2, 3]. The proposed architecture uses DAO shared memory for low-overhead communication between subsystems, while preprocessing operations such as normalization, denoising, and spatial transformations are executed directly on the GPU. This design minimizes end-to-end latency and reduces transfer overhead between acquisition, inference, and control stages.

The system was validated in closed-loop operation on the PAPHYRUS[4, 7] bench at the Observatoire de Haute-Provence using a non-modulated pyramid wavefront sensor. The controller estimates more than 200 Zernike modes and sustains operation at about 700 Hz with approximately 1 ms latency. In addition, comparisons with classical reconstruction approaches show improved correction performance in terms of residual error and Strehl ratio, supporting the feasibility of deep-learning-based RTC for future AO systems.

2. METHODOLOGY

Figure 1. Overview of the proposed real-time control architecture. Camera frames are exchanged through DAO shared memory and processed on the GPU, where preprocessing and Transformer Neural Network inference are executed before sending the reconstructed Zernike coefficients to the wavefront control stage.

Figure 1 shows the information flow of the proposed real-time control pipeline. Light measured by the non-modulated pyramid wavefront sensor is recorded by the camera, and each acquired frame is written to a DAO shared memory channel. This shared-memory architecture enables low-overhead communication between the different RTC subsystems and supports high-rate data exchange within the host computer.

The acquired camera frame is then transferred to the GPU, where the full preprocessing stage is executed. These operations include image normalization, rotation, cropping of the pupil regions, and additional processing required to format the pyramid wavefront sensor measurements as input to the neural network. By performing these operations directly on the GPU, unnecessary device transfers are minimized and the data remain in GPU memory before inference.

Once preprocessing is completed, the processed frame is passed to the Transformer Neural Network, which estimates 209 Zernike modes from the pyramid wavefront sensor signal. The network output is then written back to a memory location accessible by the DAO RTC framework, allowing the reconstructed coefficients to be used by the wavefront control system to compute the deformable mirror command and apply the correction in closed loop.

This end-to-end GPU-based implementation reduces communication overhead between acquisition, preprocessing, inference, and correction stages, helping the controller satisfy the latency requirements of real-time adaptive optics operation.

2.1 Real-time inference optimization

Although Transformer Neural Networks, and in particular the GCViT (Global Context Vision Transformer) model, provide strong wavefront reconstruction capability, their direct deployment in PyTorch is too slow to satisfy the timing constraints required for real-time adaptive optics control. In our implementation, the PyTorch baseline reaches only about 80 Hz, which is far below the frequency required for stable closed-loop operation. For this reason, the neural reconstructor was optimized using NVIDIA TensorRT, which enables faster inference through graph optimization and more efficient execution on GPU hardware.

To evaluate the impact of this optimization, we compared three implementation levels: the original PyTorch model, a TensorRT-optimized version executed from Python, and a fully GPU-based implementation in which both preprocessing and inference are performed on the device. In addition, FP16 and FP32 execution modes were tested in order to assess the trade-off between numerical precision and computational efficiency.

Figure 2. Comparison of execution frequency for the different neural network deployment strategies. The PyTorch baseline provides the lowest throughput, while TensorRT significantly improves inference speed. The highest performance is achieved when both preprocessing and inference are executed on the GPU in a full end-to-end implementation.

As shown in Fig. 2, TensorRT substantially increases the achievable execution frequency. When the optimized engine is executed from Python, the system reaches frequencies above 500 Hz, already within a range that makes real-time implementation feasible. In this configuration, a difference is observed between numerical precisions, with FP32 performing slightly better than FP16 in our setup. This behavior may be related to the specific characteristics of the hardware and software pipeline used in the experiment.

The highest performance is obtained when the full real-time pipeline is executed on the GPU. In this end-to-end implementation, the execution frequency reaches approximately 700 Hz, since host-device transfers are minimized and computational overhead outside the neural network itself is reduced. These results show that model optimization alone is not sufficient: achieving real-time AO performance also requires optimizing the complete control pipeline.

3. RESULTS

3.1 On-Sky

After optimizing the neural reconstructor for real-time AO operation, the controller was deployed on the PAPHYRUS bench at the Observatoire de Haute-Provence in France, which is coupled to a 1.52 m telescope. The full GPU implementation was used for the on-sky closed-loop experiments.

During the first observing night, closed-loop tests were performed to evaluate the correction performance in terms of Strehl ratio (SR). In open-loop operation, the measured SR was approximately 5%. After closing the loop, the system reached SR values in the range of 20–25%. Figure 3(a) shows representative sequences in open-loop operation, closed-loop operation, and a transition from open loop to closed loop, demonstrating a rapid increase in SR and a stable correction regime.

Figures 3(b) and 3(c) show the integrated point spread functions (PSFs) obtained over the same observation interval in open-loop and closed-loop conditions, respectively. The closed-loop PSF exhibits a significantly stronger concentration of light in the core, confirming that the controller improves image quality under on-sky conditions.

During the second observing night, the system was again tested at 700 Hz using the full GPU implementation. In addition to closing the loop with the neural-network reconstructor, we compared its performance with the

Figure 3. On-sky closed-loop performance obtained during the first observing night on the PAPHYRUS bench using the full GPU implementation. (a) Strehl ratio evolution for representative open-loop, closed-loop, and open-to-closed-loop transition sequences. (b) Integrated PSF in open-loop operation. (c) Integrated PSF in closed-loop operation. The closed-loop result shows a clear increase in light concentration in the PSF core.

linear reconstructor routinely used in PAPHYRUS. Both approaches were tested on the same optical bench and with the same pyramid wavefront sensor. However, the linear reconstructor required a modulation of 5 to achieve these results, whereas the neural-network-based controller operated with the non-modulated sensor.

Throughout this night, the open-loop SR was approximately 10%. In closed loop, the neural-network reconstructor reached SR values in the range of 20–23%, although with larger temporal fluctuations. These variations may be associated with changes in the atmospheric conditions during the observations. By comparison, the linear reconstructor achieved SR values of about 18–20%, with a more stable temporal behavior.

Figure 4. On-sky comparison obtained during the second observing night on the PAPHYRUS bench at 700 Hz. (a) Strehl ratio evolution in open loop and in closed loop using the neural-network reconstructor and the linear reconstructor. (b) Integrated PSF in open-loop operation. (c) Integrated PSF obtained with the linear reconstructor. (d) Integrated PSF obtained with the neural-network reconstructor.

Figure 4(a) shows the SR evolution during open-loop operation and during closed-loop correction with both the neural-network and the linear reconstructors. Figures 4(b), 4(c), and 4(d) present the integrated PSFs for the open-loop case, the linear reconstructor, and the neural-network reconstructor, respectively.

3.2 Preliminary server-side evaluation

In addition to the on-sky experiments presented above, we also evaluated smaller Transformer variants (GCViT and PVT_V2) in server-side simulations in order to explore higher inference rates. These tests were not performed on the telescope and should therefore be considered preliminary. Their purpose was to assess whether alternative architectures could further reduce inference time while preserving reconstruction performance.

Figure 5(a) shows that, once again, the baseline implementations are not sufficient to reach the execution frequencies required for real-time AO control. However, after TensorRT optimization, these smaller models achieve substantially higher inference rates, reaching approximately 1500 Hz for GCViT and 2250 Hz for PVT_V2.

Figure 5(b) presents the standard deviation of the correction for the different models, including both the baseline and optimized neural network implementations, as well as the non-modulated linear reconstructor. All

Figure 5. Preliminary server-side evaluation of alternative Transformer models under simulated conditions with $D/r_0 = 75$. (a) Inference rate for each model and deployment mode, including the baseline and full-GPU implementations. (b) Standard deviation of the correction obtained with the different neural network models, together with the non-modulated linear reconstructor. (c) Strehl ratio achieved by the same models and by the non-modulated linear reconstructor.

neural network models reduce the standard deviation, indicating that they are able to close the loop correctly. By contrast, the non-modulated linear reconstructor attempts to do so but does not succeed, leading to a larger fluctuation of the error.

Finally, Fig. 5(c) compares the Strehl ratio obtained with the same models. The neural-network reconstructors reach a stable SR of approximately 25%. Only small differences are observed between the baseline and optimized implementations, with the non-optimized versions reaching an SR that is approximately 2% lower. In contrast, the non-modulated linear reconstructor reaches an SR of about 5%.

4. CONCLUSIONS

In this work, we demonstrated the real-time deployment of a Transformer-based controller for Adaptive Optics using NVIDIA TensorRT and the DAO RTC framework. By combining model optimization, mixed-precision inference, and a full GPU implementation of the control pipeline, the system achieved closed-loop operation at 700 Hz on the PAPHYRUS bench.

The on-sky experiments confirmed that the proposed approach is not only computationally feasible, but also effective under real observing conditions. The controller was able to close the loop successfully, improving the Strehl ratio and concentrating more light in the PSF core. These results show that optimized deep-learning-based reconstructors can be used in real telescope systems for wavefront correction.

In side-by-side on-sky tests against the conventional linear reconstructor used in PAPHYRUS, the neural-network-based controller achieved comparable performance, despite operating with a non-modulated pyramid wavefront sensor, whereas the linear reconstructor required modulation to reach similar results. This highlights the potential of deep learning methods to simplify AO architectures while maintaining competitive correction performance.

Finally, the preliminary server-side evaluation of smaller Transformer variants showed that even higher inference rates are achievable while preserving reconstruction quality in simulation. These results open the door to the use of more compact and faster optimized models in future AO systems, enabling higher correction frequencies and extending the applicability of deep-learning-based RTC architectures for next-generation astronomical instrumentation.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

ANID Magister Nacional 2225105. Agencia Nacional de Investigación y Desarrollo (ANID) ANILLOS ATE220022 and ATE220057. Fondos de Desarrollo de la Astronomía Nacional QUIMAL 220006 and GEMINI 32220027. Fondo Nacional de Desarrollo Científico y Tecnológico (FONDECYT) EXPLORACION 13220234.

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